

Useful Simple Trust:

exploring practical AI applications
across an employee-owned consultancy

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

Useful Simple
Trust

Purpose-driven consultancy
for our changing environment

Useful Simple Trust:

exploring practical AI applications
across an employee-owned consultancy

When artificial intelligence became more impressive and accessible in 2023, staff at **Useful Simple Trust** began to explore how emerging tools such as ChatGPT might support their consultancy work across sustainability and the built environment.

The employee-owned group of companies provides strategic advisory, engineering and design services to a wide range of clients. And as AI technology accelerates, the organisation is aiming to move beyond ad hoc experimentation towards a more structured, responsible approach to AI adoption.

“We were seeing a lot of hype,” says Ian Small, Lead Innovation Consultant at Expedition, a Useful Simple Trust company that focuses on sustainable design and engineering. “At first, we trialed things like meeting note generators and document summarisation, but we wanted to understand how AI could genuinely support our workflows – and how to do that in the right way.”

Credit: usefulsimple.co.uk

Through Innovate UK's BridgeAI programme, Useful Simple Trust was matched with Independent Scientific Advisor Professor James Brusey of Coventry University, giving the organisation access to academic expertise as it shaped its AI strategy. Rather than arriving with a fixed set of use cases in mind, the team used its early sessions with James to map opportunities and explore where AI could add value to the company's operations. "It was a bit chicken-and-egg," says Ian. "We had some ideas in motion, but we wanted to make sure we weren't missing obvious use cases and that what we were already building was designed properly."

With James's guidance, the organisation focused on three key workstreams. The first explored an agentic retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) workflow, allowing teams to interrogate large collections of internal infrastructure-related documents and research papers through a conversational interface. The second centred on AI-supported coding – known as 'vibe coding' – where staff without programming backgrounds used generative AI tools to prototype small applications relevant to their own workflows, such as turning PDFs into vector files or selecting specific locations on a map. The third examined how AI might support report writing – not by replacing authors, but by rethinking how reports are structured, developed and reviewed.

A truly engaging moment in the collaboration was a full-day, in-person workshop led by James, where teams presented their ideas and applications as works-in-progress. "James spent time talking to each team, giving them targeted feedback," says Rachel De Matei, Senior Consultant at Expedition. "He helped our employees identify tools, approaches or improvements they hadn't considered – and at the end, everyone had a working prototype to show for it. What's really interesting is that people have started forming little communities around this work. Teams are sharing what they've been experimenting with, showing each other what they've built, and learning from one another as they go."

James adds: "Useful Simple Trust was a brilliant company to work with and an inspiration to me. I often use their example of how to approach AI adoption when talking to other businesses. The key things were a willingness to explore, making sure everyone was included in the journey, and not being afraid to take on new ways of thinking and doing."

Ian and Rachel say that success at this stage is less about 'bottom line' metrics and more about building internal understanding and confidence around how AI can be used responsibly across the organisation.

Ian concludes: "It took something like ten years to really exploit the potential of the electric motor in manufacturing, because at first people were attempting to apply it in the same way as the steam engine. We feel it's similar with AI: if you just try to shoehorn it into existing processes, you don't get the full benefit. You have to rethink how work is designed around it."

"James provided really valuable coaching and technical input – particularly around how we structured our work. That external support helped us move much faster than we would have done on our own. It allowed us to keep heading in the right direction and maintain our momentum when it comes to implementing AI."

Rachel De Matei,
Senior Consultant, Expedition (Useful Simple Trust)

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree and BSI.

Acknowledgement

This case study is published as part of the **Innovate UK BridgeAI programme**, under the Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) offer delivered by The Alan Turing Institute. The ISA initiative provides transformative, evidence-based support to SMEs across BridgeAI's priority sectors, empowering them to harness AI for strategic growth and practical impact.

We gratefully acknowledge the contributions of **Ian Small**, Lead Innovation Consultant and **Rachel De Matei**, Senior Consultant at Expedition and **Professor James Brusey**, Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute, whose insights and engagement were invaluable to the development of this case study.

We would also like to express our appreciation to **Alexandra Araujo Alvarez**, Senior Research Community Manager for BridgeAI and **Dominica D'Arcangelo**, Programme Manager, for their leadership and support throughout this work. We further acknowledge **Stuart Gillespie** for his role as technical writer for this and other case studies within the ISA offer.

This work is led by **Dr Vera Matser**, Head of Strategic Capabilities and Principal Investigator for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute.

For any comments, questions, or collaboration opportunities with BridgeAI, please email: bridgeAI@turing.ac.uk

Authors and Contributors

Stuart Gillespie: Technical Writer (0009-0003-1402-0184)

Ian Small: Lead Innovation Consultant at Expedition (Useful Simple Trust)

Rachel De Matei: Senior Consultant at Expedition (Useful Simple Trust)

Prof James Brusey: The Alan Turing Institute, Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI (0000-0002-2710-6927)

Alexandra Araujo Alvarez: The Alan Turing Institute, Senior Research Community Manager (0009-0008-6607-3815)

This publication is shared under CC-BY 4.0 License on Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20160607](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20160607)

Learn more at bridgeai.net

The
Alan Turing
Institute

